

Point Photon Flux Estimate in a Hollow Cylindrical Lead-CaskOlaseni M. Bello^{1,2}, Norehan M. Nor¹ and Wan Muhamad S. Wan Hassan¹¹Department of Physics, Universiti Teknologi Malaysia, UTM, Johor Bahru 81310, Malaysia.²Department of Physics, Nigeria Police Academy, Wudil, Kano 71310, Nigeria.

Abstract: This study is an effort to mimic and quantify the radiation absorption in a short-range radiotherapy procedure. A hollow cylindrical lead-cask was constructed and a modifiable MCNP code was developed to model the cask geometry. The model code simulates the cask with the execution of tally F75 to estimate the collisional point flux, ϕ_c and radiative point flux, ϕ_r . The collisional and radiative flux were measured for different energies (1-20MeV) at constant displacement (1cm), they are also measured for different positions (1-10cm) at constant energy (1MeV). The result from simulation indicate reduction in the flux as displacement increases (at constant energy), and the flux increases with increase in energy (at constant displacement). Relevant 6th order polynomial relations were generated from the curves of the collisional and radiative flux. The absorb dose, D and the kerma, K were calculated from the flux to estimate the quotient D/K for energy range 1MeV to 10MeV. For the 1cm constant displacement procedure, the mean D/K in percentages are 92.7% for energy range 1MeV to 4MeV and 86.9% for 6MeV to 10MeV. For the 1MeV constant energy procedure, the mean D/K was 94.4% for the entire 1cm to 10cm displacement. Also, the cask was filled with a tissue substitute and exposed to x-ray in a diagnostic facility, the D/K obtained for 70kVp to 122kVp at 100cm machine distance was approximately 70%. The cask model MCNP code is reliable within the range of distance and energy studied.

Keywords: Lead Cask; Point Photon Flux; Collisional Flux; Radiative Flux; MCNP; Photon Exposure.

Email: belloolaseni@gmail.com

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1.0 Introduction

MCNP is a state of the art code in the assessment of radiation dosimetry[1] and a means to accurate radiation planning procedure. MCNP is based on Monte Carlo method that is widely applicable in different area of studies[2]. The use of high radiation dose at very short distances like 1cm is becoming a norm in the treatment of cancer but the effect on nearest organs is however a challenge[3]. Although, the benefits of short range irradiation are enormous but the damage to normal tissue is a concern[4]. This makes the radiation planning procedure very challenging[5] because the dose received from radiotherapy procedure has a link with the overall survival rate of the subject[6]. This, and perhaps the re-irradiation of subjects[7], [8] made radiation therapy procedure a palliative option in the recent past[9]. It is important to estimate the dose as the radiation travels in the subject. Short range radiotherapy procedures use guided radiations, this study use the lead-cask to guide the radiation while estimating the dose at various energies and positions.

2.0 Material and Method

A lead cask is made from two pipes of the same height, 10.0cm but different diameters, 4.0cm and 2.3cm (Figure 1a and 1b). Lead was used to fill the gap between the two pipes, to make the lead appear cylindrical. MCNP code (appendix A) was developed to model the cask geometry (Figure 1c). Effort to use tally *F4 to estimate volume fluence and tally *F8 to estimate the energy received by the volume proved abortive, perhaps due to the small diameter or the short range. This is one of the problems attributed to small and deep seated organs in the body[10]. Tally F75 is hereby used to measure the collisional, ϕ_c and the radiative, ϕ_r flux from a point on the axis of the model. The number of particles sampled was 10^8 and the computer used was Acer Aspire C22-860 intel core-i3 64-bit OS, 2.70GHz speed and 4.00GB RAM.

The basic photon creation calculations in MCNP is useful for the estimation of the g-factor according to equation 8. The estimated g-factor in this study and the mass energy absorption coefficient, $\frac{\mu_{en}}{\rho}$ obtained from NIST Data Library are substituted in equation 9 to estimate the mass energy transfer coefficient, $\frac{\mu_{tr}}{\rho}$. The absorb dose

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was calculated from equation 10 and kerma from equation 11. The ratio of the absorb dose, D to kerma, K (D/K) were calculated to ascertain the amount of kerma dose that was absorbed. This ratio, D/K is an acceptable conversion coefficient[11]. In addition, the space inside the cask was filled with a soft tissue substitute and exposed to x-ray in a diagnostic facility, readings were taken with 100cm machine distance settings for 70kVp to 122kVp and the dose was measured. The D/K from x-ray experiment was calculated. This is against the background that there is no interaction between the environment and the flux within the hollow chamber of the lead-cask.

3.0 Results and Discussion

The average simulation run time for the 10^8 particles was 18.01minutes for the constant energy procedure. For the constant position procedure, the minimum run time was 17.74minutes and the maximum was 43.61minutes, the run time increases with increase in the magnitude of the photon energy. The collisional and the radiative flux alongside their respective relative errors were retrieved directly from MCNP result chart for the constant energy and the constant position procedures (Table1 and Table 2). Their behaviours are presented

as Figure 2 and Figure 3; and the corresponding relationships are presented as equation 2,3, 5 and 6. The collisional and the radiative photon energy flux were estimated and equation 1 and 4 represent their respective relations with distance and photon energy respectively. The error in the photon energy flux estimates was derived using equation 7. The absorb dose to kerma, D/K account for the amount of the kerma dose that is eventually absorbed. Varying the distance from 1cm to 10cm at constant energy of 1MeV, the percentage of the kerma dose that was absorbed, D/K remains 94.4% throughout the range. At 1cm and varying the irradiation energy from 1MeV to 10MeV, the mean D/K in percentage for 1MeV to 4MeV is 92.7% and 86.9% for 6MeV to 10MeV. Effort to vary the energy at constant 100cm source-detector distance yield flux values with very high relative error, making the values useless. The mean D/K at 1cm for 1MeV-10MeV is 89.8%. The absorb dose to kerma, D/K in percentage, obtained from the exposure to x-ray recorded a minimum of 61%, mean of 69.32% and maximum of 76% for 70kVp to 122kVp.

3-1-Tables, Figures and Equations

Table 1: Photon flux at varying positions and constant photon energy, (E=1MeV)

cm	φ_c	$RE(\varphi_c)$	φ_r	$RE(\varphi_r)$	$\varphi_c + \varphi_r$	$\psi = E(\varphi_c + \varphi_r)$	$RE(\psi)$
1	1.57E-02	0.0004	1.28E-02	0	2.85E-02	2.85E-02	0.0004
2	8.03E-03	0.0012	5.85E-03	0.0001	1.39E-02	1.39E-02	0.0012
3	4.02E-03	0.002	2.65E-03	0.0001	6.67E-03	6.67E-03	0.0020
4	2.13E-03	0.0043	1.29E-03	0.0002	3.41E-03	3.41E-03	0.0043
5	1.19E-03	0.0054	6.66E-04	0.0003	1.85E-03	1.85E-03	0.0054
6	6.82E-04	0.0039	3.64E-04	0.0005	1.05E-03	1.05E-03	0.0039
7	4.21E-04	0.01	2.08E-04	0.0006	6.29E-04	6.29E-04	0.0100
8	2.65E-04	0.0083	1.23E-04	0.0009	3.88E-04	3.88E-04	0.0083
9	1.71E-04	0.0052	7.41E-05	0.0010	2.45E-04	2.45E-04	0.0053
10	1.21E-04	0.0255	4.60E-05	0.0014	1.67E-04	1.67E-04	0.0255

φ_c = Collisional Flux, φ_r = Radiative Flux, RE = Relative Error, ψ = Photon Energy Flux, $RE(\psi)$ = Estimated from Equation 7

Table 2: Photon flux at varying energies and constant position (1cm)

E (MeV)	φ_c	RE(φ_c)	φ_r	RE(φ_r)	$\varphi_c + \varphi_r$	$\psi = E(\varphi_c + \varphi_r)$	RE(ψ)
1	1.57E-02	0.0004	1.28E-02	0	2.85E-02	2.85E-02	0.0004
2	1.91E-02	0.0003	1.54E-02	0.0001	3.45E-02	3.45E-02	0.0003
4	2.14E-02	0.0004	1.64E-02	0.0003	3.78E-02	3.78E-02	0.0005
6	2.28E-02	0.0006	1.66E-02	0.0006	3.94E-02	3.94E-02	0.0009
8	2.39E-02	0.0009	1.68E-02	0.0011	4.07E-02	4.07E-02	0.0014
10	2.51E-02	0.0014	1.71E-02	0.0019	4.22E-02	4.22E-02	0.0024
12	2.62E-02	0.002	1.74E-02	0.0029	4.36E-02	4.36E-02	0.0035
14	2.74E-02	0.0027	1.78E-02	0.0040	4.52E-02	4.52E-02	0.0048
16	2.84E-02	0.0032	1.82E-02	0.0050	4.66E-02	4.66E-02	0.0059
18	2.97E-02	0.0041	1.87E-02	0.0064	4.84E-02	4.84E-02	0.0076
20	3.09E-02	0.0049	1.93E-02	0.0078	5.01E-02	5.01E-02	0.0092

E = Energy, φ_c = Collisional Flux, φ_r = Radiative Flux, ψ = Photon Energy Flux, RE = Relative Error, (ψ) = Est from Equ 7

Table 3: Absorb dose to kerma ratio and the mean values

E (MeV)	D/K ST	Mean	D/K B	Mean	D/K ST	Mean	D/K B	Mean	cm
1	9.44E-01		9.44E-01		94.4	94.4	94.4	94.4	1
2	9.33E-01		9.33E-01		94.4		94.4		2
4	9.03E-01	9.27E-01	9.03E-01	9.27E-01	94.4		94.4		3
6	8.86E-01		8.86E-01		94.4		94.4		4
8	8.69E-01		8.69E-01		94.4		94.4		5
10	8.52E-01	8.69E-01	8.52E-01	8.69E-01	94.4		94.4		6
					94.4		94.4		7
					94.4		94.4		8
					94.4		94.4		9
					94.4		94.4		10

Constant Position: 1cm

Constant Energy: 1MeV

D/K = Absorb Dose/Kerma, ST = Soft Tissue, B = Bone, cm = Distance, Point Detector to Rad Source

Figure 1: a and b: Construction of Cask, c: Lead Cask Geometry

Figure 2: Collisional and Radiative Point Photon Flux vs Distance at Constant Energy of 1MeV

Figure 3: Collisional and Radiative Point Photon Flux vs Energy at Constant position of 1cm

Figure 4: Absorb Dose and the Kerma vs Energy

$$\psi @ 1\text{MeV} = 2\text{E-}06x^6 + 6\text{E-}05x^5 - 0.0009x^4 + 0.0071x^3 - 0.0276x^2 + 0.0443x + 0.0056 \quad (1)$$

x = distance between the point detector and the radiation source, $R^2 = 0.9999$

$$\phi_c @ 1\text{MeV} = 4\text{E-}08x^6 - 2\text{E-}06x^5 + 6\text{E-}05x^4 - 0.0007x^3 + 0.005x^2 - 0.0184x + 0.0298 \quad (2)$$

x = distance between the point detector and the radiation source, $R^2 = 1$

$$\phi_r @ 1\text{MeV} = 1\text{E-}07x^6 - 6\text{E-}06x^5 + 0.0001x^4 - 0.0011x^3 + 0.0061x^2 - 0.0193x + 0.0269 \quad (3)$$

x = distance between the point detector and the radiation source, $R^2 = 1$

$$\psi @ 1\text{cm} = -1\text{E-}08u^6 + 7\text{E-}07u^5 - 2\text{E-}05u^4 + 0.0003u^3 - 0.0013u^2 + 0.0433u - 0.0138 \quad (4)$$

u = Photon Energy (MeV), $R^2 = 1$

$$\phi_c @ 1\text{cm} = -9\text{E-}09u^6 + 6\text{E-}07u^5 - 2\text{E-}05u^4 + 0.0002u^3 - 0.0018u^2 + 0.007u + 0.0104 \quad (5)$$

u = Photon Energy (MeV), $R^2 = 0.9996$

$$\phi_r @ 1\text{cm} = -1\text{E-}08u^6 + 7\text{E-}07u^5 - 2\text{E-}05u^4 + 0.0003u^3 - 0.0018u^2 + 0.0063u + 0.0082 \quad (6)$$

u = Photon Energy (MeV), $R^2 = 0.9962$

$$RE(\psi) = \sqrt{(RE(\phi_c))^2 + (RE(\phi_r))^2} \quad (7)$$

ϕ_c = Collisional Flux, ϕ_r = Radiative Flux, ψ = Photon Energy Flux, $RE(\psi)$ = Relative Error in ψ

$$g = g \text{ factor} = \frac{\text{Bremsstrahlung} + \text{Positron Annihilation} + \text{Flourescence 1 \& 2}}{\text{Photon Energy}} \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{\mu_{en}}{\rho} = \frac{\mu_{tr}}{\rho} (1 - g) \quad (9)$$

ρ = Density, $\frac{\mu_{en}}{\rho}$ = Mass Eenergy Absorption Coeff., $\frac{\mu_{tr}}{\rho}$ = Mass Energy Transfer Coeff.

$$\text{Absorb Dose, } D = \psi \left(\frac{\mu_{en}}{\rho} \right) \quad (10)$$

$$\text{Kerma, } K = \psi \left(\frac{\mu_{tr}}{\rho} \right) \quad (11)$$

4-Conclusion

The estimated point photon flux obtained from simulation reduces as the distance increases under constant photon energy while the flux increases with increase in energy under constant source-detector distance. Absorb dose, D and the kerma, K estimated from the flux also increases as the energy increases. The mean of D/K from simulation is 89.8% for the range 1MeV to 10MeV at 1cm source-detector distance. From experiment at 100cm machine distance, the mean D/K for the range 70kVp to 122kVp is

approximately 70%. It is reasonable to suppose that considering the difference in the distance used, there is an agreement between the results from simulation and experiment. The model MCNP code (appendix A) developed in this study is reliable for the estimation of point photon flux.

5-Declarations

5-1-Author Contributions

Conceptualization, Olaseni Bello; methodology, Olaseni Bello; software, Olaseni Bello; validation, Olaseni Bello, Norehan Nor and Wan

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Muhamad Wan Hassan; formal analysis, Olaseni Bello; investigation, Olaseni Bello; resources, Olaseni Bello; data curation, Olaseni Bello; writing—original draft preparation, Olaseni Bello; writing—review and editing, Olaseni Bello; visualization, Olaseni Bello; supervision, Norehan Nor and Wan Muhamad Wan Hassan; project administration, Wan Muhamad Wan Hassan; funding acquisition, Norehan Nor and Olaseni Bello. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

5-2-Data Availability Statement

Data is contained within the article and supplementary material.

5-3-Funding

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5-4-Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript.

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Appendix A

MCNP Code for a Hollow Cylindrical Lead Cask

c By Olaseni M. Bello, Norehan M. Nor, Wan Muhammad S. Wan Hassan

c Cell Cards

2 1 -1.04 -11 imp:p=1 \$ Soft Tissue

1 2 -11.342 11 -10 imp:p=1 \$ Lead

3 0 10 imp:p=0 \$ Void Outside Cask

4 3 -1.293e-3 -22 10 11 imp:p=1 \$ air

5 0 22 imp:p=0 \$ universe

6 4 -22.56 -22 23 imp:p=1 \$ Source

c Surface Cards

10 CZ 2 \$ Outer Cask Cylinder

11 CZ 1.15 \$ Inside Cask Cylinder

22 C/Z 0 0 5 \$ air

23 PZ 4 \$ Source

c Data Cards

c

mode p

phys:p

nps 1e8

sdef erg=20.0 pos= 0 0 11 par=2 \$ energy, location, particle type

f75:p 1.15 1.15 10 1.15 \$ Point Detector

m1 1000 10.454E-02 6000 22.663E-02 7000 2.490E-02 8000 &
63.525E-02 11000 0.112E-02 12000 0.013E-02 14000 0.030E-02 &
15000 0.134E-02 16000 0.204E-02 17000 0.133E-02 19000 &
0.208E-02 20000 0.024E-02 26000 0.005E-02 30000 0.003E-02 &
37000 0.001E-02 40000 0.001E-02 \$ Soft Tissue from ORNL Phantom

m2 82000 1

m3 6000 -0.000124

7000 -0.755288

8000 -0.231781

18000 -0.012877

m4 77193 -1 \$Ir